

Adsorption of Sodium Linoleate in Preference to that of Sodium Oleate on the Surface of Nickel and Copper.

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Rideal (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1923, 19, 90) from a study of the relative rates of hydrogenation of the salts of cinnamic and phenylpropionic acids in presence of colloidal palladium observed that at low concentrations of the sols, the phenylpropionate is hydrogenated twice as fast as the cinnamate. He suggests that it is not due to preferential adsorption of the more unsaturated salt, but that the salts are not desorbed from the surface till completely saturated and that the phenylpropionate takes up two hydrogen molecules from palladium in the same time as the cinnamate takes up one. But most of the work on hydrogenation of oils involves the possibility of preferential hydrogenation of the more unsaturated glycerides (Moore, Richter and van Arsdel, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1917, 9, 451; Richardson, Knuth and Milligave, *Amer. Chem. Soc.*, Sept. Meeting, 1923).

The present investigation was undertaken with the object of studying the effect of double bonds in adsorption processes at catalyst surfaces. The sodium salts of oleic and linoleic acids were chosen for study. The catalysts used were copper and nickel. If, (as is usually assumed) straight-chain fatty acids do not lie flat on the surface but stand upright, being adsorbed by the end radicle like $-\text{COOH}$ group, one need not expect preferential adsorption; but if the molecules lie flat being multiply adsorbed through the agency of double bonds (Burk, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1926, 30, 1134), then one could account for preferential adsorption of the substance having greater number of double bonds over the other with a smaller number of double bonds.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of soap.:—The soaps were prepared by the methods of McBain. Alcoholic solution of sodium hydroxide was added to alcoholic solutions of the acids till the acids were neutralised. The soaps were washed several times with alcohol, and dried in a vacuum desiccator. The sample of sodium oleate was perfectly white and melted

between 233-34°. The linoleate was soxhleted with petrol and repeatedly crystallised from methyl alcohol and dried (m. p. 244°, decomp.).

Preparation of nickel.—Nickel carbonate was precipitated by the action of a cold solution of sodium carbonate saturated with carbon dioxide on a saturated solution of nickel nitrate. It was washed free from nitrate and dried at 100°, reduced at 320° for 3 hours in a current of dry electrolytic hydrogen, free from oxygen. Nickel reduced below 270° was found to be pyrophoric and could not be worked with. Nickel reduced at 320° was stable and was always kept in a vacuum desiccator except when taken out for weighing.

Preparation of copper.—Dark-red copper oxide was precipitated from a concentrated solution of copper sulphate by a concentrated solution of sodium hydroxide. It was washed thoroughly with distilled water till free from traces of alkali. The filtre cake was dried at 100°. The oxide when reduced at 200° was very pyrophoric. So it was reduced at 320° by a slow current of dry electrolytic hydrogen, free from oxygen. The copper was orange-red in colour, made into uniform powder and kept in a desiccator.

Method of work.—The soap solutions employed were between 0.1-0.5%. The method of estimating the concentration of soaps in solution before and after adsorption was by the use of Donnan's drop pipette (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1899, 31, 42). The number of drops in a known volume of the solution of various concentrations was first noted. The change in the drop number with concentrations at 30° is given in Table I. The pipette was always cleaned and dried before each observation.

TABLE I.

		Temperature 30°								
% of soap	0.000	0.050	0.100	0.200	0.250	0.400	0.500	
Drop. Nos.	{	Sod. oleate	...	173	303	378	422	429	446	455
		Sod. linoleate	...	173	236	277	330	347	358	368

Weighed quantities of the catalysts in contact with 50 c.c. of soap solutions of different concentrations in well stoppered bottles were kept in an accurately controlled thermostat at 30° for a day. The drop numbers of solutions after adsorption were found out. The concentrations of the soap solutions after adsorption were read off from the

drop number-concentration graph drawn with the help of Table I. The value of the concentrations of solutions before and after adsorption gave the figures for the amount of soap adsorbed from 100 c.c. of solution. Table II gives the summary of the results.

TABLE II.

Nickel.

Wt. of catalyst.	Soap conc.	Drop No. after adsorption		Amount adsorbed from 100 c.c.	
		Oleate.	Linoleate.	Oleate.	Linoleate.
0.5 g.	0.2 %	418	305	0.0025	0.0574
	0.4	445	343	0.0100	0.1624
	0.5	450	336	0.0574	0.2850
1.0	0.1	357	267	0.0230	0.0125
	0.2	411	301	0.0324	0.0625
	0.4	442	335	0.0500	0.1874
	0.5	447	324	0.0900	0.3144
2.5	0.1	255	261	0.0700	0.0220
	0.2	372	293	0.1074	0.0774
	0.4	435	322	0.1100	0.2174

Copper.

0.5	0.2	412	281	0.0300	0.0500
	0.4	439	304	0.0744	0.2550
	0.5	448	325	0.0800	0.3100
1.0	0.2	408	266	0.0400	0.1140
	0.5	447	324	0.0800	0.3124
2.5	0.4	431	303	0.1400	0.2575
	0.5	443	222	0.1374	0.3174

The results are of a preliminary nature. However, it appears that for concentrations of 0.2 % and more, the linoleate is adsorbed more in preference to the oleate. A detailed investigation at low concentrations would be interesting.

